

The efficacy of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding substance abuse among students at a selected school of Puducherry, India.

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ABSTRACT

Substance abuse and illegal trade are now common vices in society. Drugs and alcohol may be used by students to avoid the pressures of daily life and temporarily alleviate their mental health challenges. This leads to a cycle of addiction and further mental health problems. Their lack of knowledge about substance abuse and the appropriate preventive measures is unsatisfactory. The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of a structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding substance abuse among school students in a selected school in Puducherry. A convenience sampling technique was employed to select samples from grades 9 and 10. Demographic variables and a knowledge questionnaire were used to gather data in the pre-test. A structured teaching programme (STP) was administered to the samples. A post-test was conducted after 15 days of STP. The study revealed that STP has a significant positive impact on knowledge levels regarding substance abuse. Among 120 students, all had obtained adequate knowledge regarding substance abuse after STP. The STP was found to be extreme effective in improving the knowledge regarding substance abuse among school students. In this study, there was a significant association found between level of knowledge of school students regarding substance abuse and their demographic variables residence and number of siblings.

KEYWORDS: Substance abuse, knowledge, school students.

INTRODUCTION

Substance abuse is becoming a bigger issue globally, and regrettably, it is increasingly prevalent among young children and teenagers, who are just starting their careers but become embroiled in this issue for a variety of reasons.

Every year on June 26, the globe observes globe Drug Day, also known as the International Day against Drug abuse and Illicit Trafficking, to increase collaboration and action toward ending drug misuse worldwide. Millions of people around the world are impacted by the complex issue of the global drug crisis.

Newpane S (2023) conducted a study to evaluate the knowledge and attitudes on substance abuse among 630 higher secondary school students in Kathmandu. Data were collected using demographic data and self-administered questionnaire. The study results shows that the more than half (59.2%) respondents had poor knowledge whereas only 8.6% had moderate knowledge and as only few had good knowledge on substance abuse.

Ramzan R and Ishrat (2024) assessed the effectiveness of STP on knowledge regarding substance abuse among 50 adolescents in selected school, Budgam, Kashmir. Pre experimental one group pre-test and post-test design was used. Data were collected using demographic data and self-structured questionnaire. The results show that in the pre-test, 75% students had inadequate knowledge, 25% students had moderately adequate knowledge and none had adequate knowledge regarding substance abuse whereas in the post-test, 89% of students had adequate knowledge, 11% had moderately adequate knowledge and none had inadequate knowledge regarding substance abuse.

Nurses play an important role in the early detection of health problems, nutritional screening for adolescents, and nutritional education. Through a structured teaching program, nurses educate adolescents about the health risks of substance abuse and help them develop the right attitude and practice healthy lifestyles.

METHODOLOGY

Research approach: Quantitative research design approach was adopted.

Research design: The research design for the study was one group pre-test and post-test quasi experimental design.

Setting of the study: The setting for the study was selected school in Puducherry.

Population: Population of the study was all the 9th and 10th grade students of selected School in Puducherry.

Sample and sample size: The sample for the study was 9th and 10th grade students of selected school in Puducherry. The sample size was 120 students.

Sampling technique: The sampling technique used for the study was non probability convenience sampling technique.

Criteria for sample selection:

Inclusion criteria:

- Students who were studying 9th and 10th grades.
- Students who were accepting the intervention.
- Students who were able to understand the Tamil and English languages.

Exclusion criteria:

- Students who were not willing to participate in the study.
- Students who were not available at the time of data collection.

Description of tools:

The tool used in the study consisted of two sections: **Section-A:** Demographic variables which consisted eight items such as age, gender, education status of parents, residential area, family type, religion, siblings and source of getting health information. **Section-B:** Structured self-administered knowledge questionnaire which is prepared by investigators and consisted of 20 questions. Total score was 20. Each questions carries 1 mark. Correct answer gives 1 mark and wrong answer gives 0 mark.

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Ethical clearance was obtained from Institutional ethical committee. Content validity of the tool was obtained from the experts in the field of Nursing and Bio statistics. A formal permission was obtained from the school authority to conduct the study. An assent and written informed consent was obtained from the students and their parents. A rapport was established. The pre-test knowledge was assessed using a demographic variable and a structured knowledge questionnaire regarding substance abuse among school students. A structured teaching

programme was administered. The post-test knowledge was measured 15 days after the structured teaching programme.

RESULTS

(1) Demographic data: The majority of school students were aged between 14 and 15 years, 80 (66.7%) were females, 60 (50.0%) were studying 9th and 10th standards, 76 (63.3%) were came from the rural region, 74 (61.7%) were Muslims, 43 (35.8%) students' fathers were studied up to middle school education, 60 (50.0%) students' mothers were non literate, 112 (93.3%) students' fathers were working in the private sectors.

(2) Level of knowledge of the school students regarding substance abuse

Level of knowledge	Pre-test	
	n	%
Inadequate knowledge	47	39.2%
Moderate knowledge	51	42.5%
Adequate knowledge	22	18.3%
Total	120	100 %

Above table shows the frequency and percentage distribution of level of knowledge regarding substance abuse among school students in the pre-test. Among 120 students, 51 (42.5%) of school students had moderate knowledge, 47(39.2%) had inadequate knowledge in the pre-test.

Level of knowledge	Post-test	
	n	%
Inadequate knowledge	0	0 %
Moderate knowledge	0	0 %
Adequate knowledge	120	100 %
Total	120	100 %

Above table shows the frequency and percentage distribution level of knowledge regarding substance abuse among school students in the post-test. All students 120 (100%) were gained an adequate knowledge regarding substance abuse after STP.

Knowledge score	Mean score	SD	Paired Differences	Paired t-test	p-value
Pre test	10.98	3.643	8.583	25.633	<0.001
Post test	19.56	0.646			

Above table shows the effectiveness of STP in the post-test regarding substance abuse among school students. The pre-test and post-test mean knowledge score were 10.98 and 19.56 respectively. Paired t-test score was 25.633 ($p < 0.001$), and found that there was a significant difference between pre-test and post-test level of knowledge.

(3) Association between level of pre-test knowledge regarding substance abuse among school students and their demographic variables

There was a statistically significant association found between knowledge of school students regarding substance abuse and their respect to residential area at the level of ($p < 0.05$) $p = 0.015$ and number of siblings ($p < 0.05$) $p = 0.017$. Others had no association

DISCUSSION

Knowledge regarding substance abuse among school students was assessed in this study. The majority of the students, 51 (42.5%) of the students had moderate knowledge, 47 (39.2%) had inadequate knowledge and 22 (18.3%) had adequate knowledge regarding substance abuse in the post-test. This result is supported by **Newpane S (2023)**, **Ogochukwa et al (2022)**, **Soniya M D (2022)**, **Habeeb I A, Kareem, and Sachit (2022)**, and **Bhawariya R (2020)**. All students (100%) were gained an adequate knowledge regarding substance abuse in the post-test after STP. Hence, hypothesis H_1 was accepted as there was a significant difference in the level of knowledge regarding substance abuse between in the pre-test and post-test. This result is similar to the finding of previous studies such as **Ramzan R and Ishrat (2024)**, **Tejeshwari B Vet al (2023)**, and **Signet J et al (2022)**. A significant association was found between pre-test knowledge of school students and their demographic variables such as residence ($p = 0.015$) and number of siblings ($p = 0.017$). Hence hypothesis H_2 was accepted with regards to association between pre-test knowledge of the school students and their variables such as residence and number of siblings. Other variables had no association. This result was similar to the study findings of **Kumar S S et al (2022)** and **Begam B and Devi K (2021)**.

CONCLUSION

The study was conducted among 120 school students in a selected school in Puducherry. The knowledge of school students was assessed using a self-administered structured questionnaire. The study result revealed that after STP, all students 120(100%) were gained an adequate knowledge regarding substance abuse and also association was found between the pre-test knowledge and their demographic variables such as residence and number of siblings. Hence, this study proved that the knowledge regarding substance abuse is essential to prevent use of substances and its consequences.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Nil

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